

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE FORMATION OF COORDINATION SKILLS IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES WITH ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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direction

Annotation: the study studies methods and approaches aimed at developing mobility in primary school students, as well as analyzing the impact of various types of exercise and physical activity on their physical and mental development. Particular attention is paid not only to the physical development of children, but also to the formation of their social skills, incentives to play sports and methods of play that contribute to the common interest in physical activity.

Keywords: elementary grades, physical development, game techniques, physical activity, wellness, mental development, social skills, motivation for Sports, Health Promotion, effective techniques, lesson organization

INTRODUCTION.

In modern society, there is a tendency to decrease the level of physical activity among children, which leads to various negative consequences. Elementary students are in an active physical and mental stage of development, and inactivity can negatively affect their general condition, which contributes to the development of various diseases, for example, obesity, violation of body structure", cardiovascular and other diseases.

The formation of mobility in children of small school age is an important component of their physical education. As a cardinative physical ability, it includes agility, agility and coordination of movements, which is the basis for mastering various movement skills. The development of mobility helps to improve the movement activity of children, which has a positive effect on their educational and extracurricular activities, increases general physical fitness and has a positive effect on health The modern educational system needs effective physical education methods and programs that help to develop their mobility, taking into account the age characteristics of small-

class students. The introduction of new pedagogical approaches and methodologies aimed at the formation of mobility contributes not only to increasing the level of physical fitness of students, but also to their general development and socialization.

In addition, research in the field of formation of mobility in children of small school age is of great practical importance for educators and coaches. They allow the development and implementation of effective educational programs to suit the needs and capabilities of children, as well as the adaptation of physical education to be interesting and useful for students.

The purpose of the study is to develop and substantiate effective methodologies for the formation of mobility of Primary School students in the process of physical education training in a comprehensive school, which will help improve their physical development and general physical fitness.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

-Development of methodological recommendations for the formation of mobility in physical education classes for primary classes.

- Analysis and development of recommendations for educators.

Mobility refers to the ability to perform large amplitude movements in these vapors and muscles. In children of small school age, this quality is important because it helps to coordinate movements, develop agility, patience and strength. In addition, mobility is directly related to various aspects of health, such as body structure, the Prevention of flat feet and the general physical condition of the body.

In elementary classes, various methods and techniques are used to effectively develop mobility in physical education classes. They include:

Action games

Play is the main type of activity of children of small school age. Adding action games to physical education classes helps to develop not only mobility, but also other physical qualities. These games also contribute to the formation of a positive attitude of children towards physical activity. For example:

- Puzzle games: games in which children have to move with the ball and exchange quickly with each other. It develops their agility and balance.

- Chase games: games based on children chasing each other. This improves their speed, agility and cardiovascular function.

Gymnastic exercises

The set of gymnastic exercises includes exercises aimed at developing agility and coordination of the body. These include bending the body, twists, stretches and other elements that improve Steam and muscle mobility. For example:

* Bends: forward and lateral bends. This increases the agility of the muscles of the waist and legs.

- Turns: turning the body and head in different directions. It develops the spine and improves the balance of the body.

- Stretches: muscle stretching exercises in different racurs. These exercises help to increase muscle agility and ensure freedom of movement.

These methods and exercises complexly improve the physical development of children, increase their level of physical fitness and have a positive effect on their health. These activities also arouse children's interest in physical activity, encouraging them to actively participate in physical education classes.

Elements of acrobatics and sports games. Exercises that include simple acrobatic elements and elements of sports games (such as basketball or soccer) can help develop agility, quick reaction, and overall mobility.

Outdoor activities. Physical activity in the open air (morning charging, walks, street action games) has a positive effect on the mobility and general physical condition of children.

In conclusion, it can be said that the development of mobility in physical education classes of Primary School students is the main aspect of their overall physical development. Taking into account the individual characteristics of children, regular implementation of various exercises and a gradual increase in the complexity of the load will help to form stable motor skills and stimulate interest in a healthy lifestyle. Pedagogical recommendations based on the principles of adaptation, diversity and step-by-step make it possible to effectively and effectively conduct physical education in elementary schools, which increases not only the physical, but also the psycho-emotional well-being of students.

LITERATURE USED

1. Даминов, И. А. (2023). СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ ВИДОВ БОРЬБЫ СТРАН МИРА. *Fan-Sportga*, (1), 48-52.
2. Salimov U. Pedagogical ideas of the founder of scientific pedagogy Yan Amos Komensky // *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 2 – С. 368-372.
3. Лебединская И. Г. Физкультурно-оздоровительная и спортивно-массовая работа с детьми по месту жительства // *Вестник Таганрогского института имени АП Чехова*. – 2015. – №. 2. – С. 145-149.
4. Саблина, И. В. (2013). 4. Психолого-педагогические особенности перехода детей из начальных классов в среднее звено школы. *Концепт*, (2 (18)), 102-108.
5. Дмитриева, Н. Л. (2004). Формирование профессиональной компетентности будущего учителя начальных классов сельской школы (Doctoral dissertation, [Новгор. гос. ун-т им. Ярослава Мудрого]).